

AuScope

Australia's National
Science Agency

AuScope Data Repository (Data Deposit Guidelines)

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Acknowledgement of Country

CSIRO acknowledges the Traditional Owners of the lands, seas and waters of the area that we live and work on across Australia. We acknowledge their continuing connection to their culture and pay our respects to their Elders past and present.

Photo

Characterisation image of natural mineral iron-oxide nodules. Taken with CSIRO-developed Maia x-ray imaging.

Document History

Date	Version	Change Log	Author(s)
10.01.2024	1.0	Developed the draft of the data deposit guidelines.	Anusuriya Devaraju
09.02.2024	1.1	Reviewed the document. Updated document based on the feedback received.	Lesley Wyborn, Vincent Fazio, Anusuriya Devaraju
28.05.2024	1.2	Updated the data submission flow chart and data limit requirements; included rights, country acknowledgement and photo credit.	Anusuriya Devaraju

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1 Introduction

The [AuScope Data Repository](#) is committed to preserving and offering continued access to data from **Australia's geoscience community** (e.g., NCRIS-funded projects and Australian Geoscience research communities) working on fundamental geoscience questions and grand challenges, including climate change, natural resources security and natural hazards. The repository curates and publishes geoscience research data following the [FAIR Data Guiding Principles](#). Datasets will be available openly, where applicable, through the repository with persistent identifiers and appropriate attributions to promote open science and ensure credit to researchers and AuScope and other funders. The repository is essential for geoscience research innovation in support of the [AuScope 5-Year Investment Plan](#) and [Australian Academy of Science Decadal plan for Australian Geoscience: Our Planet, Australia's Future](#).

1.1 Scope

This document provides an overview of data publication processes supported by the repository. It is **intended for data providers** (i.e., individuals who want to publish their data via the repository).

1.2 Minimum Requirements

The following are the minimum requirements for depositing your data into the AuScope Data Repository:

- Use your institution's email to log into the repository via the Australia Access Federation (AAF)
- Provide at least the required metadata. For more information, see [Metadata Requirements](#).
- Organize your data files with an easy-to-follow folder structure and make the files available in community-endorsed or open format. For file format recommendations, see [File Formats](#).
- Include supplementary files that can help users reuse your data, e.g. readme.txt files, data schema definitions, and related publications that describe the methods used to produce the data.
- Accept the author declaration available at the end of the data submission.
- Upon publishing your dataset, cite your data following the recommended format, see [Data Citation](#), where applicable.

If you have any further enquiries about the repository, please contact us via the Contact form available on the repository or email us at auscope.doi@csiro.au.

2 Data Submission and Publication Workflow

Figure 1 summarises the flow from data submission to publication with Digital Object Identifier (DOI). There are three actors involved in the publication process:

- *Data Provider*—Also known as data depositors, these include AuScope project partners, Australian geoscience researchers, and affiliates who want to curate their data through the repository.
- *Data Repository Curator* - To ensure high-quality data publication, the data editor (a member of the AuScope Data Repository team) will review the data submissions before publishing them through the repository.
- *Data Repository Engineer* – The engineer of the AuScope Data Repository team will assist with migrating large datasets from the data provider's location into the repository.

Figure 1. Data submission and publication flow.

2.1 Uploading Data via the Repository

Data providers may upload files through the repository. There are a few aspects of the uploading process that you should be aware of:

- You may upload as many files as possible. However, the maximum allowed size for **each file is 300MB**.
- Uploading files via the browser may take time, so please be patient and **do not navigate away from this page while uploading**.
- Please contact us if you receive a **timeout error** when you upload a **large** file (e.g., after 10 minutes). We will help you with the upload.

2.2 Continual Data

For continual/periodic data releases (e.g., monthly time series), please contact us via the Contact form or auscope.doi@csiro.au. The AuScope Data Repository team will work with you to plan periodic data releases and programmatically migrate your data into the repository.

3 Metadata and Data Requirements

3.1 Metadata

Before submitting data to the repository, please gather the following **mandatory** metadata:

Metadata	Description
Title	The title of the dataset should be informative and short and define technical terms and acronyms clearly.
Author(s) with contact and affiliation information	The full name of the entity, e.g. a person or organization, that created or produced the dataset with email and affiliation. If available, include the ORCID of the author.
Description	A summary describing the purpose, nature, and scope of the dataset. Provide contextual information important to the reuse of the dataset, e.g. formats, recommended tools, related resources, or limitations.
User Specified Keywords	Keywords help with the discovery of the dataset.
GCMD Science Keywords	Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords can be selected from the drop-down menu provided

Fields of Research	The area(s) of study relevant to the dataset based on the ANZSRC Fields of Research (FoR) 2020
Funding	Information about financial support for the dataset. Provide the full (official) name of the funding providers, e.g., Australian Research Council (ARC).
Project	For each funder, specify the full name of projects through which the dataset collected or produced. Include the project's persistent identifier (PID) , if available.
License	License for the distribution and sharing of the dataset. The default license the repository offers is CC BY 4.0 International . Should this license not fit your data requirements, please contact us via the Contact form or auscope.doi@csiro.au .

We encourage the data providers to incorporate the **recommended** fields below to promote data discovery and reuse:

Metadata Field	Description
Lineage	The Lineage should contain information about how the data was produced. Processes involved in the production of the data could be included here including method and instrument information, as well as links to the source datasets if used.
Locality	The locality or named place where a particular rock type, stratigraphic unit or mineral species is defined from.
Spatial Coverage	Point or area (bounding box) representing the location of the dataset with proper geographic coordinate system (also called datum). You can specify the points or bonding boxes via the map included in the submission form.
Related Resources	Associated resources (e.g. report, article, data) related to the dataset, include their persistent links, if available.

3.2 File Formats

The following are file formats recommended by AuScope, based on the [Library of Congress Recommended Formats Statement 2020-2021](#), to support data preservation and reuse. These formats are well-known and can be accessed using common tools. We will improve the format list as the data practices of the AuScope communities evolve. Please contact us if your file format is not included in the list below.

Data Types	Formats
Vector	GML, ESRI Shapefile, GeoJSON, ESRI File Geodatabase, OGC GeoPackage
Raster images	Geo-referenced TIFF, Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG), OGC GeoPackage
Data series	Comma-separated values (CSV), Tab-delimited file, HDF5, NetCDF and Zarr (for multidimensional array), domain-specific formats such as Advanced Scientific Data Format (ASDF), MTH5 (for magnetotelluric time series), SEED/miniSEED and PH5 (for seismological data), and GyPy (for geophysical data)
Still Images	PNG, TIFF, JPEG, SVG
Documents	PDF/UA, PDF/A or PDF, OpenDocument Text, Plain text (.txt)

4 Persistent Identifier and Citation

To enable permanent data access, each dataset submitted to the repository will be registered with a [Digital Object Identifier \(DOI\)](#).

The repository will generate the citation based on the following format:

Creator (PublicationYear): Title. Publisher. ResourceType. DOI

For example,

Graeme Beardsmore, Joe Hamad (2024): Gippsland and Murray Basin Fiber Optic Distributed Temperature Sensing Data. AuScope. (Dataset). <https://doi.org/10.82669/meq3cwju>

The DOI above is shown for demo only; therefore, it is not actionable.

5 Embargo

By submitting a dataset with an embargo, you can set a period of exclusive access to your dataset while citing the DOI issued for your dataset in your publications. The maximum embargo permitted is **12 months** from the date you submitted your data. The repository will restrict access to the dataset until the embargo end date. After the embargo period, it will be publicly accessible via the repository.

To share your data submission with selected users (e.g., journal article reviewers) during the embargo, please contact us with the following information:

- Dataset submitted (title and link)
- Email the person you want to share your data with. We recommend providing an official email.

6 Licensing

In line with the [National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Scheme \(NCRIS\)](#) strategy of enabling open and collaborative access, datasets submitted to the repository will be published with the most permissive license ([CC BY 4.0 International](#)), except where the context otherwise requires.